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Construction of Wannier orbitals and calculation of crystal field parameters of Ce-doped $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$

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Abstract. We present two approaches for improving the description of highly correlated 4f states in lanthanides, which are often overly delocalized and their energies are unreliable within standard Density Functional Theory (DFT). The first approach involves transforming the DFT electronic structure into Wannier functions, that are localized on an atom, enabling direct evaluation of Crystal Field Parameters. The second approach focuses on determining the effective Hubbard parameter U_{eff} , local correlation potential that is usually being considered as an adjustable parameter. Its assessment from DFT is shown on a well-studied material Ce-doped $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ garnet. The results are compared with standard spin-orbit calculation.

Keywords: Wannier orbitals; Hubbard U; Crystal Field Parameters; YAG:Ce; DFT; DOS; scintillator;

1 Introduction

The Density Functional Theory (DFT) provides an efficient approximation for many-electron systems and is therefore widely applied to inorganic crystals using Periodic Boundary Condition [1], Plane Waves [2] and Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) [3, 4]. However, for computations of crystals containing lanthanides and transition metals, the f and d bands obtained by DFT are highly delocalized and their absolute energy values are unreliable [5, 6].

Several approaches are commonly used for better description of these highly correlated systems, like GGA [7] or LSDA+U [8–10]. Another approach is so called Green Function Method [11]. It is also possible to go for hybrid functionals [12, 13], but those calculations require much bigger computational power. In the recent years, the Embedded Cluster [14] method combined with multi reference methods is being used and shows a good correspondence with experimental values [15–17]. However, their computational demand is also very high.

The Wannier transformation provides a method for obtaining Wannier orbitals $w_n(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{R})$, that are localized on an atom, unlike Bloch orbitals $\psi_{n,\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$ [18, 19]. Wannier orbitals can be used as a basis for systems under Periodic Boundary Conditions and they are not limited by Muffin Tin approximation [20]. Moreover, their mathematical form provides a better description in real space, it provides a better understanding from a chemical perspective, like chemical bonds, but also a description of highly localized and correlated $4f$ electrons of rare earths with strong spin orbit coupling. All these effects are smeared out and underestimated when using conventional DFT [21].

The strong electron-electron correlation is another essential characteristics of $4f$ electrons. Here we attempt to assess the value of effective Coulomb repulsion and exchange parameter within WIEN2k code [22–24] for Ce- $4f$ electrons considered as core states and compare it with the semiempirical value used in GGA+U method with Ce- $4f$ treated as valence states.

For demonstrating these methods, we chose a well-studied material, Ce doped $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ garnet [25–28]. The garnet structure contains three cation sites with different coordination numbers: Y - dodecahedral ($CN = 8$), Al - octahedral ($CN = 6$) and Al - tetrahedral ($CN = 4$) [29]. According to ionic radii trends [30], we assumed that Ce as a dopant only occupies the dodecahedral site.

Yttrium aluminium garnet (YAG) is a widely used material with applications ranging from scintillation detectors in high energy physics to phosphors in white light-emitting diodes [31, 32]. It has high energy conversion efficiency, high chemical and mechanical stability and short decay times [33, 34]. YAG crystals are usually grown by the Czochralski method, a technique of growth from melt allowing high-quality of single crystals with very low internal strain [35, 36]. Apart from obtaining bulk crystals, there is also demand for optical fibers, especially for high energy laser systems [37, 38].

The scintillation mechanism of YAG:Ce is connected to creation of excitons in host lattice, non-radiative energy transfer to the Ce^{3+} and $Ce : 5d-4f$ transition. In higher temperatures, the ionization barrier between Conduction Band Minimum (CBM) and $Ce : 5d$ is decreased. The emission is being stabilized by Me^{2+} codoping [35, 39].

2 Methodology

2.1 Structural optimizations

Crystal structures being used were obtained by structural optimizations. They were conducted by VASP 6.4.3 program implemented in software MedeA [40–42]. $Ce_3Al_5O_{12}$ and $CeY_5Al_{10}O_{24}$ supercells, both containing 160 atoms, were created by replacing specific yttrium atoms with cerium in $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ [43] and increasing symmetry to $Ia\bar{3}d$ and $I\bar{4}c2$, respectively. The spin polarized computation was performed with a k-point mesh $3 \times 3 \times 3$ and a cut-off energy 400 eV. All atom coordinates and cell parameters were optimized by Conjugate gradient method [44].

2.2 Wannier transformation

The calculations were performed on a virtual end-member $Ce_3Al_5O_{12}$ of the $(Y_{3-x}Ce_x)Al_5O_{12}$ solid solution. The first part of Wannier transformation was performed in Wien2k software [45]. First, the Ce- $4f$ states were brought into core and a positive constant potential 1.5 Ry was applied on them in order to get their energy closer to the Fermi level. After reaching the convergence, the Ce- $4f$ orbitals were put back to the valence shell, while all semi-core states were removed, and the unoccupied states were pushed up by 3 Ry (by applying an on-site potential) to avoid their hybridization with Ce- $4f$. By contrast, the on site potential of $\Delta = 5.4$ eV was set on O- $2p$ and O- $2s$ states as the only free parameter to adjust a proper rate of hybridization with Ce- $4f$. In the next step, a single run of eigenvalue problem (*LAPW1* program) was performed and the set of seven closely separated Ce- $4f$ bands was identified. These were then wannierized in Wannier90 program [19] [46].

2.3 Crystal field parameters and ground state multiplet splitting

The crystal field parameters $B_q^{(k)}$ (CFP) can be extracted from the transformed Wannier Hamiltonian by expanding it by means of spherical tensor operators $\hat{C}_q^{(k)}$ [45]

$$\hat{H}_{CF} = \sum_{k=2,4,6} \sum_{q=-k}^k B_q^{(k)} \hat{C}_q^{(k)} \quad (1)$$

Because the Hamiltonian must be Hermitian,

$$\left(B_{-q}^{(k)}\right)^* = (-1)^q B_q^k. \quad (2)$$

The obtained CFP were further used to solve the local atomic Hamiltonian in a form of Stevens' operator equivalents [47] [48]

$$\hat{H}_{CF} = \sum_{k,q} B_q^k \lambda_k \hat{O}_q^k. \quad (3)$$

applied on the $|M_J\rangle$ basis set corresponding to $\text{Ce}^{3+} \ ^2F_{5/2}$ ground state and $\ ^2F_{7/2}$ excited state multiplets to obtain the eigenvalues due to crystal field splitting as well as the eigenvectors for the respective three and four Kramers doublets.

2.4 Effective U parameter

The approach to determine the effective Coulomb repulsion parameter U of strongly correlated Ce-4*f* electrons is basically similar to the first preparatory step for Wannier transformation (performed in Wien2k). The Ce-4*f* orbitals of a single Ce atom are moved from the valence shell to the core and their potential is increased by applying a constant term 0.6 eV. The number of 4*f* electrons is then increased from 1.0 to 1.5 and decreased to 0.5 (reducing the number of valence electrons correspondingly), and the selfconsistent spin polarized calculation is performed (keeping the 4*f* states of all the other Ce atoms in the valence shell). The effective U_{eff} parameter is then obtained as a difference in total energies of the two cases corrected by a difference of the respective Fermi energies (shifted due to a different number of valence electrons) [49].

2.5 Spin orbit calculation

The optimized structures were also studied by VASP 6 program implemented in MedeA software package. The spin orbit magnetic calculation was conducted with k-mesh $3 \times 3 \times 3$, normal precision, cut-off energy 400 eV, and setting $U_{eff} = 7$ eV on Ce : 4*f*, obtaining the Density of States, Band Structure and Partial Charge Density.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Wannier transformation, CF parameters and ground state multiplet splitting

The Wannier transformed orbitals shown in Fig. 1 correspond to a cubic representation f_{z^3} , f_{xz^2} , f_{yz^2} , $f_{x(x^2-3y^2)}$, $f_{y(2x^2-y^2)}$, $f_{z(x^2-z^2)}$, and f_{xyz} in the order from left to right and downwards, respectively. As mentioned, they were primarily constructed with the aim of obtaining the crystal field parameters, resulting from the interaction with the potential created by nearest neighbors as well as by more distant surroundings. Hence, the electron correlations were treated within GGA only and neither spin polarization nor spin-orbit coupling were considered. Let us note that if these functions, having different radial parts, were to be further used, for instance, to determine the spin-orbit coupling parameter ξ , they would have to be first transformed back to the m_l -basis set.

The expansion of the transformed Wannier Hamiltonian in terms of Racah tensors (eq. 1) resulted in the set of parameters of the crystal field potential experienced by Ce-4*f* electrons, which are summarized in Table 1. The obtained values are compared with those reported by

Figure 1: Isovalues of Wannier functions

Mihóková et al. [50]. However, direct comparison can not be made as the two sets apparently correspond to Ce sites with different orientation of local coordination system with respect to crystal axes. In our case, we used a Ce atom whose local coordinate axes were $x' = (0, \sqrt{2}/2, -\sqrt{2}/2)$, $y' = (0, \sqrt{2}/2, \sqrt{2}/2)$ and $z' = (1, 0, 0)$ (in terms of crystal cubic coordinates).

Hence, only the sums defined by Eq. 4 are relevant [51]. The observed differences can be attributed to different structures used for calculations (virtual end-member with only Ce occupying the dodecahedral site vs. an optimized supercell with a single Ce-atom in YAG host lattice).

Table 1: Crystal field parameters B_q^k as obtained from Wannier transformation of Ce-4*f* states. Sums for the respective *k*-values (Eq. 4) are given in the lower part.

<i>k</i>	<i>q</i>	B_q^k (meV) [this work]	B_q^k (meV) [50]
2	2	-48.7	-46.6
2	0	111.2	-21.2
4	4	-189.7	-203.9
4	2	324.5	313.8
4	0	-18.6	-5.6
6	6	44.3	147.5
6	4	125.3	142.4
6	2	27.3	63.0
6	0	-224.6	-250.8
S_2		75.54	39.97
S_4		237.86	236.70
S_6		111.63	148.76

$$S_k = \left[\frac{1}{2k+1} \sum_{q=-k}^k |B_q^{(k)}|^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Although we are dealing with a single electron system, whose atomic Hamiltonian can be solved using $|m_l, m_s\rangle$ basis, we use the operator equivalents formalism (Eq. 3) to evaluate the respective matrix elements of the crystal field Hamiltonians with the $|M_J\rangle$ basis for $J = 5/2$ and $J = 7/2$, which were first treated separately. Let us note that for the ground state multiplet all terms involving $k = 6$, i.e. B_q^6 , are canceled in Eq. 3.

Firstly, solving the crystal field 6×6 Hamiltonian, the energies of three Kramers doublets were obtained, relative to the original $J = 5/2$ multiplet level. The eigenvectors and eigenvalues are presented in Table 2. Eigenvalues corresponds to the contributions of the basis states $|M_J\rangle$ to the eigenstates.

Table 2: Eigenvalues (meV) and eigenvectors (in vertical format) of CF Hamiltonian for $J = 5/2$

ϵ_1	ϵ_2	ϵ_3	ϵ_4	ϵ_5	ϵ_6
77.6	77.6	-4.85	-4.85	-72.7	-72.7
\vec{v}_1	\vec{v}_2	\vec{v}_3	\vec{v}_4	\vec{v}_5	\vec{v}_6
$\begin{bmatrix} 0.5078 \\ -0.0806 \\ 0.7088 \\ 0.1247 \\ -0.4580 \\ 0.0893 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0893 \\ 0.4580 \\ 0.1247 \\ -0.7088 \\ -0.0806 \\ -0.5078 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0033 \\ 0.8485 \\ -0.0453 \\ 0.5207 \\ -0.0737 \\ 0.0384 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0384 \\ -0.0737 \\ -0.5207 \\ -0.0453 \\ -0.8485 \\ -0.0033 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0403 \\ -0.2415 \\ -0.0215 \\ 0.4566 \\ 0.0114 \\ -0.8550 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.8550 \\ -0.0114 \\ 0.4566 \\ 0.0215 \\ -0.2415 \\ -0.0403 \end{bmatrix}$

Secondly, analogously solving a 8×8 Hamiltonian for $J = 7/2$ multiplet, energies of four Kramers doublets were obtained (Table 3).

Table 3: Eigenvalues (meV) and eigenvectors (in vertical format) of CF Hamiltonian for $J = 7/2$

ϵ_1	ϵ_2	ϵ_3	ϵ_4	ϵ_5	ϵ_6	ϵ_7	ϵ_8
110.2	110.2	-4.37	-4.37	-23.1	-23.1	-34.1	-34.1
\vec{v}_1	\vec{v}_2	\vec{v}_3	\vec{v}_4	\vec{v}_5	\vec{v}_6	\vec{v}_7	\vec{v}_8
$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0084 \\ -0.2498 \\ -0.0130 \\ -0.4416 \\ 0.0079 \\ 0.7256 \\ 0.0045 \\ 0.4645 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.4645 \\ 0.0045 \\ -0.7256 \\ 0.0079 \\ 0.4416 \\ -0.0130 \\ 0.2498 \\ -0.0084 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1004 \\ -0.0221 \\ 0.5179 \\ -0.0630 \\ 0.7983 \\ -0.0409 \\ 0.2797 \\ -0.0079 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0079 \\ 0.2797 \\ 0.0409 \\ 0.7983 \\ 0.0630 \\ 0.5179 \\ 0.0221 \\ 0.1004 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0132 \\ 0.9079 \\ 0.0025 \\ -0.3189 \\ 0.0160 \\ -0.0496 \\ -0.0457 \\ 0.2626 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.2626 \\ 0.0457 \\ -0.0496 \\ -0.3189 \\ -0.3189 \\ -0.0025 \\ 0.9079 \\ 0.0132 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.8396 \\ -0.0015 \\ -0.4483 \\ 0.0021 \\ 0.2483 \\ -0.0038 \\ -0.1801 \\ 0.0071 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.0071 \\ -0.1801 \\ 0.0038 \\ 0.2483 \\ -0.0021 \\ -0.4483 \\ 0.0015 \\ 0.8396 \end{bmatrix}$

However, the separate treatment of multiplets with different J described above assumes that the spin-orbit interaction is much stronger compared to crystal field effect and thus the energy separation between two multiplets barycentres Δ_{SO} is much larger compared to CF splitting. This assumption is, unfortunately, not met for the $\text{Ce}^{3+} \ ^2F$ term where $\Delta_{SO} \sim 0.3$ eV. Hence, after diagonalizing two intra-multiplet crystal-field Hamiltonians H_{CF}^J separately, a combined crystal-field and spin-orbit Hamiltonian was constructed in a block form

$$\tilde{H} = \begin{pmatrix} E_{5/2} & \tilde{V} \\ \tilde{V}^\dagger & E_{7/2} + \Delta_{SO}I \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{V} = U_{5/2}^\dagger H_{CF} U_{7/2}$ couples the two spin-orbit manifolds. Here, the H_{CF} matrix elements were evaluated using spherical tensor operators (Eq. 1) that can be applied on the basis states with different J . The matrices $E_{5/2}$ and $E_{7/2}$ are diagonal and contain the crystal-field eigenvalues of the respective J multiplets (with $E_{SO}(5/2) = 0$ and $E_{SO}(7/2) = \Delta_{SO} = 0.3$ eV). The unitary matrices $U_{5/2}$ and $U_{7/2}$ involve the eigenvectors of the separate CF Hamiltonians for $J = 5/2$ and $J = 7/2$ given in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The diagonalization of \tilde{H} (Eq. 5) yields the final eigenstates, which represent mixed configurations of $J = 5/2$ and $J = 7/2$. As seen from Tables 4 and 5, the mixing of both multiplets substantially affects both the resulting energies and the spectrum of the involved eigenstates. For instance, the admixture of $J = 7/2$ basis states into the lowest ground state Kramers doublet represents 10 %.

Table 4: Energy levels and coefficients for eigenstates 0–5. E_{sep} energies are eigenvalues of unitary matrices $U_{5/2}$ and $U_{7/2}$, E_{mix} are the final eigenstates after mixing $J = 5/2$ and $J = 7/2$.

E_{sep} (meV)	E_{mix} (meV)	J	M	0	1	2	3	4	5
-72.18	-76.21	5/2	-5/2	0.856	-0.002	-0.016	-0.002	0.030	0.481
-72.18	-76.21	5/2	-3/2	0.000	0.239	0.109	-0.856	-0.412	0.025
-4.48	-6.35	5/2	-1/2	-0.445	0.001	-0.496	-0.063	0.044	0.712
-4.48	-6.35	5/2	+1/2	-0.001	-0.445	0.063	-0.496	0.712	-0.044
77.57	44.27	5/2	+3/2	0.239	0.000	-0.856	-0.109	-0.025	-0.412
77.57	44.27	5/2	+5/2	0.002	0.856	0.002	-0.016	0.481	-0.030
218.34	221.59	7/2	-7/2	0.000	-0.065	-0.007	0.053	0.179	-0.011
218.34	221.59	7/2	-5/2	-0.052	0.000	-0.039	-0.005	0.001	0.010
277.88	280.76	7/2	-3/2	0.000	0.042	-0.003	0.024	0.137	-0.008
277.88	280.76	7/2	-1/2	0.051	0.000	-0.022	-0.003	0.012	0.191
296.63	298.37	7/2	+1/2	0.000	-0.051	-0.003	0.022	-0.191	0.012
296.63	298.37	7/2	+3/2	-0.042	0.000	-0.024	-0.003	-0.008	-0.137
411.02	441.57	7/2	+5/2	0.000	0.052	-0.005	0.039	-0.010	0.001
411.02	441.57	7/2	+7/2	0.065	0.000	-0.053	-0.007	-0.011	-0.179

Given the contributions of the respective $|M_J\rangle$ basis states to the ground state Kramers doublet, we can evaluate a rough estimate of the saturation magnetization for a single Ce-site in the low temperature limit $g_J M_J = 1.84 \mu_B$ (neglecting different g_J for the admixed $J = 7/2$ basis states). This estimate is lower than the free ion value $2.14 \mu_B$ due to mixing $M_J = \pm 5/2$, $M_J = \mp 3/2$ and $M_J = \pm 1/2$ states within the ground state multiplet. The value is even further reduced by the admixture of $M_J = \mp 7/2$ and $M_J = \mp 3/2$ and $M_J = \pm 1/2$ from $J = 7/2$.

3.2 Calculation of effective U_{eff} parameter for Ce-4f

Strong electron-electron correlation beyond the standard LDA/GGA functional can be treated in WIEN2k and VASP programs by applying an effective parameter of Coulomb and exchange interaction $U_{eff} = U - J$ as an additional potential acting on a specific site and orbital (Ce-4f in our case). Using the method described above, we obtained $U_{eff} = 9.8$ eV, a value referred to Ce-4f as core states, which were however purposefully shifted in energy towards the valence states by an additional potential of 0.6 eV. Despite that, the obtained value lies somewhere

Table 5: Energy levels and coefficients for eigenstates 6–13. E_{sep} energies are eigenvalues of unitary matrices $U_{5/2}$ and $U_{7/2}$, E_{mix} are the final eigenstates after mixing $J = 5/2$ and $J = 7/2$.

$E_{sep}(\text{meV})$	$E_{mix}(\text{meV})$	J	M	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
-72.18	-76.21	5/2	-5/2	0.005	0.062	0.074	0.000	0.042	0.000	0.150	0.000
-72.18	-76.21	5/2	-3/2	0.068	-0.005	0.000	0.058	0.000	-0.017	0.000	-0.139
-4.48	-6.35	5/2	-1/2	-0.004	-0.056	0.014	0.000	0.061	0.000	0.190	0.000
-4.48	-6.35	5/2	+1/2	-0.056	0.004	0.000	-0.014	0.000	-0.061	0.000	0.190
77.57	44.27	5/2	+3/2	0.005	0.068	-0.058	0.000	0.017	0.000	-0.139	0.000
77.57	44.27	5/2	+5/2	0.062	-0.005	0.000	-0.074	0.000	-0.042	0.000	0.150
218.34	221.59	7/2	-7/2	0.823	-0.060	0.000	0.232	0.000	-0.113	0.000	-0.461
218.34	221.59	7/2	-5/2	0.012	0.170	0.934	0.000	-0.221	0.000	-0.213	0.000
277.88	280.76	7/2	-3/2	-0.461	0.034	0.000	-0.064	0.000	-0.555	0.000	-0.673
277.88	280.76	7/2	-1/2	-0.019	-0.252	-0.245	0.000	-0.790	0.000	-0.460	0.000
296.63	298.37	7/2	+1/2	0.252	-0.019	0.000	-0.245	0.000	-0.790	0.000	0.460
296.63	298.37	7/2	+3/2	0.034	0.461	-0.064	0.000	-0.555	0.000	0.673	0.000
411.02	441.57	7/2	+5/2	-0.170	0.012	0.000	0.934	0.000	-0.221	0.000	0.213
411.02	441.57	7/2	+7/2	-0.060	-0.823	0.232	0.000	-0.113	0.000	0.461	0.000

between the limits of an isolated ion and a simple GGA functional applied to the valence states described by delocalized Bloch functions. Between these limiting cases the screening gradually increases and thus U_{eff} is decreased. Hence, considering a slightly higher screening when Ce-4*f* orbitals are brought back to valence shell, the empirical value $U_{eff} = 7 \text{ eV}$ used in our VASP calculations seems to be a reasonable choice.

3.3 DFT calculations including spin-orbit coupling

The obtained Densities of States reveal a Conduction Band (CB) predominantly composed of Y-4*d*, Al-3*p* and Ce-5*d* states with a small admixture of O-2*p*, while the Valence Band (VB) is mainly formed by O-2*p* and hybridized with the above mentioned metal valence orbitals. In the Band Gap, there is a narrow fully occupied band of predominant Ce-4*f* character. In the virtual Ce₃Al₅O₁₂ end-member, the band width is 0.48 eV, while for a diluted Ce-dopant on Y site a very sharp peak (0.026 eV) is observed. The Band Gap (excluding Ce-4*f*) is 3.84 eV and 4.11 eV, respectively. These values are indeed substantially underestimated compared to the experimentally reported bandwidths, see e.g. 7.1 eV [52], which is a well-known shortcoming of DFT methods [21]. It can be partially eliminated, for example, by using computationally more demanding hybrid functionals [53]. Both VB Maximum and CB Minimum (CBM) are mainly composed of O-2*p* and Y-4*d*, the former ones dominating in VB, while the latter ones in CB.

The Partial Charge Density was calculated for twelve bands situated in the band gap of Ce₃Al₅O₁₂ electronic structure, which have a major Ce-4*f* character. The last four bands above VBM (closest to E_F) are presented in Figure 3. The isosurfaces are mostly in shape of eight equal lobes oriented in the vertices of a cube. That means that the lobes are oriented to the centers of the faces of the square antiprism, a coordination polyhedron of the dodecahedral site. Even though all Ce sites have the same site symmetry, the manifolds corresponding to respective bands reveal different shapes located on the individual sites, and only summation over all twelve bands restores the overall charge density, which is equivalent to all sites 4.

The total magnetic moment resulting from the GGA+U+SO calculations, $0.34\mu_B$, represents the contribution of spin part ($\sim 1\mu_B$) and the orbital part ($\sim 1.3\mu_B$) being oriented in opposite directions for a single electron in Ce-4*f* sub-shell.

The projected wave function characters of the same four bands of the mid-gap states are

Figure 2: Density of states of $\text{Ce}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (left) and $\text{CeY}_5\text{Al}_{10}\text{O}_{24}$ (right) structures. Total DOS is black, Ce-4*f* is purple, Ce-5*d* is green, Y-4*d* is blue, Al-3*p* in tetrahedral site is yellow, Al-3*p* in octahedral site is orange, O-2*p* is red.

Figure 3: Partial charge densities isoplanes of $\text{Ce}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ of the highest four bands of total 12 bands conta. Ce-4*f* has major contribution. Visualized by Vesta [54].

Figure 4: Partial charge density isoplane of $\text{Ce}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ of 12 mid-gap states summed up together. Ce-4*f* has major contribution. Visualized by Vesta [54].

presented in Table 6. Their comparison with the eigenvectors of crystal field Hamiltonian diagonalization would require a more detailed and complex analysis, as the transformation from the cubic to $|M_J\rangle$ representation is necessary for this purpose.

Table 6: Projected wave function characters of each orbital in bands 489–492. Spin channels $\downarrow\downarrow$ and $\text{Re}(\uparrow\downarrow)$ have zero contribution in the whole mid-gap state.

	Band 489		Band 490		Band 491		Band 492	
Energy (eV)	5.9132		5.9370		5.9809		5.9886	
Spin	$\uparrow\uparrow$	$\text{Im}(\uparrow\downarrow)$	$\uparrow\uparrow$	$\text{Im}(\uparrow\downarrow)$	$\uparrow\uparrow$	$\text{Im}(\uparrow\downarrow)$	$\uparrow\uparrow$	$\text{Im}(\uparrow\downarrow)$
Ce(4 <i>f</i>)	0.820	0.304	0.772	0.236	0.780	0.288	0.768	0.280
Ce(5 <i>d</i>)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
O(2 <i>p</i>)	0.112	0.032	0.168	0.136	0.144	0.096	0.152	0.128
Ce(4 <i>f</i> _{y^3x^2})	0.122	0.014	0.142	0.082	0.120	0.012	0.100	-0.052
Ce(4 <i>f</i> _{xyz})	0.012	0.004	0.008	-0.008	0.012	0.004	0.008	0.008
Ce(4 <i>f</i> _{yz^2})	0.158	0.148	0.120	0.116	0.148	0.146	0.164	0.156
Ce(4 <i>f</i> _{z^3})	0.120	-0.072	0.160	-0.136	0.120	-0.064	0.080	-0.008
Ce(4 <i>f</i> _{xz^2})	0.158	0.148	0.120	0.116	0.148	0.146	0.164	0.156
Ce(4 <i>f</i> _{zx^2})	0.128	0.048	0.080	-0.016	0.112	0.032	0.152	0.072
Ce(4 <i>f</i> _{x^3})	0.122	0.014	0.142	0.082	0.120	0.012	0.100	-0.052
O(2 <i>p</i> _{y})	0.040	0.012	0.060	0.056	0.056	0.040	0.040	0.028
O(2 <i>p</i> _{z})	0.032	0.008	0.048	0.024	0.032	0.016	0.072	0.072
O(2 <i>p</i> _{x})	0.040	0.012	0.060	0.056	0.056	0.040	0.040	0.028

4 Conclusion

We have studied Ce doped $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ garnet and transformed its Ce-4*f* bands into Wannier wave functions, that enabled us to calculate the Crystal Field Parameters and determine the Zero Field

Splitting by constructing its local Hamiltonian, including spin-orbit coupling, mixing $J = 5/2$ and $J = 7/2$ multiplets.

We also calculated Hubbard parameter $U_{eff} = 9.8 \text{ eV}$, that is in line with the expected trend of increasing screening effect from localized atomic limit towards collective electrons limit.

Moreover, we compared the result with standard spin-orbit magnetic calculation and showed the difference between charge densities of individual bands and Wannier functions.

We also determined saturation magnetization in the low temperature limit from crystal field Hamiltonian and from spin-orbit magnetic calculation in VASP, obtaining the values $1.84\mu_B$ and $0.34\mu_B$, respectively. The observed difference demonstrates the effect of enhanced delocalization imposed by DFT treatment compared to localized atomic Hamiltonian.

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References

- [1] Makov G and Payne M C 1995 *Physical Review B* **51** 4014–4022
- [2] Kresse G and Furthmüller J 1996 *Physical Review B - Condensed Matter and Materials Physics* **54** 11169–11186
- [3] Blöchl P E 1994 *Physical Review B* **50** 17953–17979
- [4] Blaha P, Schwarz K, Sorantin P and Trickey S 1990 *Computer Physics Communications* **59** 399–415
- [5] Tam D W, Colonna N, Alarab F, Strocov V N, Gawryluk D J, Pomjakushina E and Kenzelmann M 2024 *npj Quantum Materials* **9** 26
- [6] Rani D, Jana S, K Niranjana M and Samal P 2024 *Journal of Physics Condensed Matter* **36**
- [7] Perdew P, Burke K and Ernzerhof M 1996 *Physical Review Letters* **77** 3865–3868
- [8] Dudarev S L, Botton G A, Savrasov S Y, Humphreys C J and Sutton A P 1998 *Physical Review B* **57** 1505–1509
- [9] Liechtenstein A I, Anisimov V I and Zaanen J 1995 *Physical Review B* **52** R5467–R5470
- [10] Dudarev S, Liu P, Andersson D, Stanek C, Ozaki T and Franchini C 2019 *Physical Review Materials* **3** 083802
- [11] Kotani T and Akai H 1996 *Physical Review B* **54** 16502–16514
- [12] Gou G Y, Bennett J W, Takenaka H and Rappe A M 2011 *Physical Review B* **83** 205115
- [13] Schwabe T and Grimme S 2007 *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **9** 3397–3406
- [14] Larsson E D, Krośnicki M and Velyazov V 2022-10-01 *Chemical Physics* **562** 111549
- [15] Barandiarán Z, Joos J S L 2022 *Luminescent Materials: A Quantum Chemical Approach for Computer-Aided Discovery and Design* (Springer)
- [16] Larsson E D and Velyazov V 2023 *Journal of Chemical Physics* **159** 114117
- [17] Joos J J, Van Der Heggen D, Amidani L, Seijo L and Barandiarán Z 2021 *Physical Review B* **104** L201108

- [18] Marzari N and Vanderbilt D 1997 *Physical Review B - Condensed Matter and Materials Physics* **56** 12847–12865
- [19] Mostofi A A, Yates J R, Lee Y S, Souza I, Vanderbilt D and Marzari N 2008-05-01 *Computer Physics Communications* **178** 685–699
- [20] Marzari N, Mostofi A A, Yates J R, Souza I and Vanderbilt D 2012 *Reviews of Modern Physics* **84** 1419–1475
- [21] Becke A D 2014 *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **140** 18A301
- [22] Blaha P, Schwarz K, Tran F, Laskowski R, Madsen G K H and Marks L D 2020 *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **152** 074101
- [23] Novák P, Boucher F, Gressier P, Blaha P and Schwarz K 2001 *Physical Review B* **63** 235114
- [24] Blaha P, Schwarz K, G M, Kvasnicka D and Luitz J 2001 *WIEN2k: An Augmented Plane Wave plus Local Orbitals Program for Calculating Crystal Properties* vol 28 (Technische Universität Wien, Wien)
- [25] Blasse G and Brill A 1967 *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **47** 5139–5145
- [26] Markovskiy A, Radomski P, Dewo W, Gorbenko V, Fedorov A, Runka T and Zorenko Y 2025 *Materials Research Bulletin* **182** 113141
- [27] Syrotych Y, Gorbenko V, Witkiewicz-Lukaszek S, Zorenko T, Kaczmarek M, Pejchal J, Mares J A, Kucerkova R, Nikl M, Kamada K, Yoshikawa A and Zorenko Y 2024 *Optical Materials: X* **24** 100372
- [28] Laguta V, Buryi M, Babin V, Machek P, Zazubovich S, Bartosiewicz K, Kurosawa S, Yamaji A, Yoshikawa A, Uličná K, Chlan V, Štěpánková H and Nikl M 2022 *Journal of Materials Chemistry C* **11** 1346–1359
- [29] Almessiere M A, Ahmed N M, Massoudi I, Al-Otaibi A L, Al-shehri A A and Shafouri M A 2018 *Optik* **158** 152–163
- [30] Shannon R D 1976 *Acta Crystallographica Section A* **32** 751–767
- [31] Lucchini M, Gundacker S, Lecoq P, Benaglia A, Nikl M, Kamada K, Yoshikawa A and Auf-ray E 2017 *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* **852** 1–9
- [32] Schlotter P, Schmidt R and Schneider J 1997 *Applied Physics A* **64** 417–418
- [33] Dormenev V, Brinkmann K T, Kazlou D, Moritz M, Novotny R, Peter M and Zaunick H G 2023 *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science* **70** 1392 – 1397
- [34] Babin V, Blazek K, Krasnikov A, Nejezchleb K, Nikl M, Savikhina T and Zazubovich S 2005 *physica status solidi (c)* **2** 97–100
- [35] Zapadlík O, Nikl M, Polák J, Průša P and Linhart V 2022 *Optical Materials: X* **15**
- [36] Sidletskiy O, Gerasymov I, Boyaryntseva Y, Arhipov P, Tkachenko S, Zelenskaya O, Bryleva K, Belikov K, Lebbou K, Dujardin C, Büchner B and Grynyov B 2021 *Crystal Growth & Design* **21** 3063–3070
- [37] Dragic P, Law P C, Ballato J, Hawkins T and Foy P 2010 *Opt. Express* **18** 10055–10067

- [38] Ballato J, Hawkins T, Foy P, Kokuoz B, Stolen R, McMillen C, Daw M, Su Z, Tritt T M, Dubinskii M, Zhang J, Sanamyan T and Matthewson M J 2009 *Journal of Applied Physics* **105** 053110
- [39] Nikl M, Kamada K, Babin V, Pejchal J, Pilarova K, Mihokova E, Beitlerova A, Bartosiewicz K, Kurosawa S and Yoshikawa A 2014 *Crystal Growth & Design* **14** 4827–4833
- [40] Kresse G and Furthmüller J 1996 *Physical Review B* **54** 11169–11186
- [41] Kresse G and Furthmüller J 1996 *Computational Materials Science* **6** 15–50
- [42] Materials Design I 2025 Medea[®] software materials modeling environment
- [43] Euler F and Bruce J A 1965 *Acta Crystallographica* **19** 971–978
- [44] Bitzek E, Koskinen P, Gähler F, Moseler M and Gumbusch P 2006 *Physical Review Letters* **97** 170201
- [45] Novák P 2017 *Calculation of crystal field parameters and magnetism with Wannier functions Manual* (WIEN2k-Textbooks)
- [46] Kuneš J, Arita R, Wissgott P, Toschi A, Ikeda H and Held K 2010-11-01 *Computer Physics Communications* **181** 1888–1895
- [47] Smith D and M T J H 1966 *Proceedings of the Physical Society* **89** 779
- [48] Lueken H 2008 *Course of lectures on magnetism of lanthanide ions under varying ligand and magnetic fields*
- [49] Madsen G K H and Novák P 2007 *Calculating the effective U in APW methods. NiO* (WIEN2k-Textbooks)
- [50] Mihóková E, Novák P and Laguta V 2015 *Journal of Rare Earths* **33** 1316–1323
- [51] Leavitt R P 1982 *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **77** 1661–1663
- [52] Ueda J, Dorenbos P, Bos A J, Kuroishi K and Tanabe S 2015 *J. Mater. Chem. C* **3** 5642–5651
- [53] Krukau A V, Vydrov O A, Izmaylov A F and Scuseria G E 2006 *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **125** 224106
- [54] Momma K and Izumi F 2011 *Journal of Applied Crystallography* **44** 1272–1276